

Note on the “structure” of partitions $P(n,k)$ and of partitions that accept null or negative addenda

Introduction

For partition $P(n,k)$, it could be useful, particularly in probability-related investigations, to know how many parts of $P(n,k)$ contain an addendum a or a group of addenda $aa, aaa, \dots$

This is what here is called “structure” of the partition.

Reminder of notations

$P(n,k) = m$ means that there are m different ways of writing n as the sum of exactly k non-zero addenda. The order of the addenda does not matter. Each way is called a “part” of the partition. For example, $P(6,3) = 3$ tells us that 6 can be obtained in three ways with three addenda: 411, 321 and 222.

$PZ(n,k)$ indicates a partition where the zero addendum is also allowed.

$P1(n,k)$ indicates a partition where, in addition to zero, addendum -1 is also allowed. We could go on.

$P(a,b) = P(c,d)$ means that the two partitions have the same number of parts, which are not necessary equal.

Composition $C(n,k)$ is a partition that takes into account the order of the addenda.

1. “Structure” of partitions

The number of parts that contain the addendum a or addenda aa , or aaa etc. is given by the formulas:

$$- \text{ Parts with } a \quad P(n-a, k-1) - P(n-2a, k-2) \quad (1)$$

$$- \text{ Parts with } aa \quad P(n-2a, k-2) - P(n-3a, k-3) \quad (2)$$

$$- \text{ Parts with } aaa \quad P(n-3a, k-3) - P(n-4a, k-4)$$

(3)

In general, the number of parts with t times a is given by:

$$- P(n-ta, k-t) - P(n-a(t+1), k-t-1) \quad (4)$$

Note that it is assumed that $P(0,0) = 1$ (the only way to write 0 without addenda, like the well-known $P(0)=1$).

For example, if we want to know in how many parts of the partition $P(20,6) = 90$ the group 55 appears, using (2) we have:

$$P(20-2*5, 6-2) - P(20-3*5, 6-3) = P(10, 4) - P(5, 3) = 9 - 2 = 7$$

as can be verified in Appendix 1 (taken from 'Partition Calculator for Integer Numbers') which lists the 90 parts of $P(20,6)$. In fact, there are the following seven groups:

755111 655211 554411 554321 554222 553331 553322

2. Justification of equations (1), (2), (3), ... and (4)

The total number of parts with a is, of course, given by $P(n - a, k - 1)$, but some parts may have groups $aa, aaa, aaaa \dots$ etc. So, the total number of parts with only one addendum a is obtained by subtracting from $P(n-a, k-1)$ the number of parts with at least the group aa , i.e. $P(n - 2a, k - 2)$. Thus we have the equation (1).

Similarly, the number of parts with aa , given by (2), is $P(n-2a, k-2) - P(n-3a, k-3)$ and so on.

The total number of parts of $P(n, k)$ containing a is given by the sum of equations (1), (2), (3), ... and is therefore equal to $P(n-a, k-1)$.

3. "Structure" of partition $P(n, k)$

The procedure described by equations (1), (2), (3), ... can be applied to all addenda contained in $P(n, k)$ ranging from 1 to $n-k+1$. So, we have a "structure" of the partition $P(n, k)$. For example, Appendix 2 gives in detail the structure of $P(20, 6)$.

The number of elements a in the partition is given by the sum of the results of equations (1), (2), (3), ... multiplied by the relative t . For example, the number of the addendum 3 in partition $P(20, 6)$ is:

$t = 1$	number of parts with 3	$P(17, 5) - P(14, 4) = 47 - 23 = 24$
$t = 2$	number of parts with 33	$P(14, 4) - P(11, 3) = 23 - 10 = 13$
$t = 3$	number of parts with 333	$P(11, 3) - P(8, 2) = 10 - 4 = 6$
$t = 4$	number of parts with 3333	$P(8, 2) - P(5, 1) = 4 - 1 = 3$
$t = 5$	number of parts with 33333	$P(5, 1) - P(2, 0) = 1 - 0 = 1$

So the number of the addendum 3 in $P(20, 6)$ is $1*24 + 2*13 + 3*6 + 4*3 + 5*1 = 85$.

Note also that the sum of the groups containing 3, 33, 333, 3333, 33333 (that is: $24 + 13 + 6 + 3 + 1 = 47$) is given by the first member of equation (1), which in the example is $P(17, 5) = 47$.

4. A general check

Repeating the procedure for all possible a of the partition (from 1 to $n-k+1$) gives the total number of addenda in the partition, which obviously is equal to the value of $P(n, k)$ multiplied by k .

In the example in Appendix 2, for $P(20, 6) = 90$, the total number of addenda is 540, equal to $90*6$.

This constitutes an indirect verification of the correctness of equations (1), (2), (3), ...

5. "Structure" of partitions $PZ(n,k)$, $P1(n,k)$, ... admitting null or negative addenda¹

Equation (4) also holds for generalized partitions $PZ(n,k)$, $P1(n,k)$, $P2(n,k)$, and so on. Just replace $P(n,k)$ with the generalized partition. In this way, (4) becomes:

$$P, Z, 1, 2, \dots (n - ta, k - t) - P, Z, 1, 2, \dots (n - a(t + 1), k - t - 1) \quad (5)$$

For example, for partition $P1(6,4)$, which admits as addenda also zero and -1 and which is given in Appendix 3, we have:

- Number of parts with 0 $(n = 6; t = 1; a = 0)$ $P1(6,3) - P1(6,2) = 12 - 5 = 7$
- Number of parts with 00 $(n = 6; t = 2; a = 0)$ $P1(6,2) - P1(6,1) = 5 - 1 = 4$
- Number of parts with $-1 -1$ $(n = 6; t = 2; a = -1)$ $P1(6 + 2,2) - P1(6 + 3,1) = 6 - 1 = 5$

Appendix 1 $P(20,6) = 90$

15	1	1	1	1	1	8	7	2	1	1	1	6	6	3	3	1	1
14	2	1	1	1	1	8	6	3	1	1	1	6	6	3	2	2	1
13	3	1	1	1	1	8	6	2	2	1	1	6	6	2	2	2	2
13	2	2	1	1	1	8	5	4	1	1	1	6	5	5	2	1	1
12	4	1	1	1	1	8	5	3	2	1	1	6	5	4	3	1	1
12	3	2	1	1	1	8	5	2	2	2	1	6	5	4	2	2	1
12	2	2	2	1	1	8	4	4	2	1	1	6	5	3	3	2	1
11	5	1	1	1	1	8	4	3	3	1	1	6	5	3	2	2	2
11	4	2	1	1	1	8	4	3	2	2	1	6	4	4	4	1	1
11	3	3	1	1	1	8	4	2	2	2	2	6	4	4	3	2	1
11	3	2	2	1	1	8	3	3	3	2	1	6	4	4	2	2	2
11	2	2	2	2	1	8	3	3	2	2	2	6	4	3	3	3	1
10	6	1	1	1	1	7	7	3	1	1	1	6	4	3	3	2	2
10	5	2	1	1	1	7	7	2	2	1	1	6	3	3	3	3	2
10	4	3	1	1	1	7	6	4	1	1	1	5	5	5	3	1	1
10	4	2	2	1	1	7	6	3	2	1	1	5	5	5	2	2	1
10	3	3	2	1	1	7	6	2	2	2	1	5	5	4	4	1	1
10	3	2	2	2	1	7	5	5	1	1	1	5	5	4	3	2	1
10	2	2	2	2	2	7	5	4	2	1	1	5	5	4	2	2	2
9	7	1	1	1	1	7	5	3	3	1	1	5	5	3	3	3	1
9	6	2	1	1	1	7	5	3	2	2	1	5	5	3	3	2	2
9	5	3	1	1	1	7	5	2	2	2	2	5	4	4	4	2	1
9	5	2	2	1	1	7	4	4	3	1	1	5	4	4	3	3	1
9	4	4	1	1	1	7	4	4	2	2	1	5	4	4	3	2	2
9	4	3	2	1	1	7	4	3	3	2	1	5	4	3	3	3	2
9	4	2	2	2	1	7	4	3	2	2	2	5	3	3	3	3	3
9	3	3	3	1	1	7	3	3	3	3	1	4	4	4	4	3	1
9	3	3	2	2	1	7	3	3	3	2	2	4	4	4	4	2	2
9	3	2	2	2	2	6	6	5	1	1	1	4	4	4	3	3	2
8	8	1	1	1	1	6	6	4	2	1	1	4	4	3	3	3	3

¹ See Tavazza G. Generalization of partitions $P(n,k)$ with the admission of null or negative addenda (10.5281/zenodo.7271835)

Appendix 2

Detail of the “structure” of $P(20,6) = 90$ (90*6=540 addenda)

- The number of parts with 1 is 70, given by $P(19,5) = 70$ divided as follows:
 - Parts with 1 $P(19,5) - P(18,4) = 70 - 47 = 23$
 - Parts with 11 $P(18,4) - P(17,3) = 47 - 24 = 23$
 - Parts with 111 $P(17,3) - P(16,2) = 24 - 8 = 16$
 - Parts with 1111 $P(16,2) - P(15,1) = 8 - 1 = 7$
 - Parts with 11111 $P(15,1) - P(14,0) = 1 - 0 = 1$

The number of 1 is: $1*23 + 2*23 + 3*16 + 4*7 + 1*5 = 150$

- The number of parts with 2 is 57 given by $P(18,5) = 57$ divided as follows:
 - Parts with 2 $P(18,5) - P(16,4) = 57 - 34 = 23$
 - Parts with 22 $P(16,4) - P(14,3) = 34 - 16 = 18$
 - Parts with 222 $P(14,3) - P(12,2) = 16 - 6 = 10$
 - Parts with 2222 $P(12,2) - P(10,1) = 6 - 1 = 5$
 - Parts with 22222 $P(10,1) - P(8,0) = 1 - 0 = 1$

The number of 2 is: $1*23 + 2*18 + 3*10 + 4*5 + 5*1 = 114$

- The number of parts with 3 is 47 given by $P(17,5) = 47$ divided as follows:
 - Parts with 3 $P(17,5) - P(14,4) = 47 - 23 = 24$
 - Parts with 33 $P(14,4) - P(11,3) = 23 - 10 = 13$
 - Parts with 333 $P(11,3) - P(8,2) = 10 - 4 = 6$
 - Parts with 3333 $P(8,2) - P(5,1) = 4 - 1 = 3$
 - Parts with 33333 $P(5,1) - P(2,0) = 1 - 0 = 1$

The number of 3 is: $1*24 + 2*13 + 3*6 + 4*3 + 5*1 = 85$

- The number of parts with 4 is 37 given by $P(16,5) = 37$ divided as follows:
 - Parts with 4 $P(16,5) - P(12,4) = 37 - 15 = 22$
 - Parts with 44 $P(12,4) - P(8,3) = 15 - 5 = 10$
 - Parts with 444 $P(8,3) - P(4,2) = 5 - 2 = 3$
 - Parts with 4444 $P(4,2) - P(0,1) = 2 - 0 = 2$

The number of 4 is: $1*22 + 2*10 + 3*3 + 4*1 = 59$

- The number of parts with 5 is 30 given by $P(15,5) = 30$ divided as follows:
 - Parts with 5 $P(15,5) - P(10,4) = 30 - 9 = 21$
 - Parts with 55 $P(10,4) - P(5,3) = 9 - 2 = 7$
 - Parts with 555 $P(5,3) - P(0,2) = 2 - 0 = 2$

The number of 5 is: $1*21 + 2*7 + 3*2 = 41$

- The number of parts with 6 is 23 given by $P(14,5) = 23$ divided as follows:
 - Parts with 6 $P(14,5) - P(8,4) = 23 - 5 = 18$
 - Parts with 66 $P(8,4) - P(2,3) = 5 - 0 = 5$

The number of 6 is: $1 \cdot 18 + 2 \cdot 5 = 28$

- The number of parts with 7 is 18 given by $P(13,5) = 18$ divided as follows:
 - Parts with 7 $P(13,5) - P(6,4) = 18 - 2 = 16$
 - Parts with 77 $P(6,4) - P(-1,3) = 2 - 0 = 2$

The number of 7 is: $1 \cdot 16 + 2 \cdot 2 = 20$

- The number of parts with 8 is 13 given by $P(12,5) = 13$ divided as follows:
 - Parts with 8 $P(12,5) - P(4,4) = 13 - 1 = 12$
 - Parts with 88 $P(4,4) - P(-4,3) = 1 - 0 = 1$

The number of 8 is: $1 \cdot 12 + 2 \cdot 1 = 14$

- The number of parts with 9 is 10 given by $P(11,5) = 10$ divided as follows:
 - Parts with 9 $P(11,5) - P(2,4) = 10 - 0 = 10$

The number of 9 is: $1 \cdot 10 = 10$

- The number of parts with 10 is: 7 $P(10,5) = 7$
- The number of parts with 11 is: 5 $P(9,5) = 5$
- The number of parts with 12 is: 3 $P(8,5) = 3$
- The number of parts with 13 is: 2 $P(7,5) = 2$
- The number of parts with 14 is: 1 $P(6,5) = 1$
- The number of parts with 15 is: 1 $P(5,5) = 1$

The total number of elements of $P(20,6)$ is:

$$150 + 114 + 85 + 59 + 41 + 28 + 20 + 14 + 10 + 7 + 5 + 3 + 2 + 1 + 1 = 540, \text{ i.e. } 90 \cdot 6$$

This is also an indirect way of calculating the value $P(20,6) = 90$

Appendix 3

$$P1(6,4) = 23$$

9	-1	-1	-1
8	0	-1	-1
7	1	-1	-1
7	0	0	-1
6	2	-1	-1
6	1	0	-1
6	0	0	0
5	3	-1	-1
5	2	0	-1
5	1	1	-1
5	1	0	0
4	4	-1	-1
4	3	0	-1
4	2	1	-1
4	2	0	0
4	1	1	0
3	3	1	-1
3	3	0	0
3	2	2	-1
3	2	1	0
3	1	1	1
2	2	2	0
2	2	1	1